

Liposomal encapsulation of omega-3 and lipoic acid conjugate for cow milk fortification

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Abstract

α -Linolenic acid (ALA) and α -lipoic acid (LA) are well known bioactives. However, they are susceptible to oxidation. The present study was conducted to encapsulate chia oil as the source of ALA and LA, together in a liposomal formulation, to protect these biomolecules. LA inclusion complex with hydroxypropyl β -cyclodextrin exhibited encapsulation efficiency of $86.09 \pm 2.17\%$. The inclusion complex was characterized using FTIR, NMR, and DSC. Nanoliposome formulated with LA inclusion complex and chia oil showed encapsulation efficiency of $80.24 \pm 0.49\%$ and $76.38 \pm 0.58\%$, respectively, with an average particle size of 52.19 ± 7.0 nm, and moderate repulsion among the particles. Cow milk fortified with LA and chia oil nanoliposome showed supplementation of 236.16 mg LA and 719.52 mg ALA in one serving (240 mL) of milk. This fortification would contribute to the functionality of cow milk, by improving its nutritional attributes even further than naturally present.

Keywords: α -lipoic acid, α -linolenic acid, inclusion complex, nanoliposomes, milk fortification

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1. Introduction

In recent years, oxidation in the body has become a threat in most developed and developing countries. Various strategies have emerged currently for a healthy lifestyle, and therapeutic interventions are also aiming to reduce the oxidative damages in the body (Ramis et al., 2015). There are various bioactive compounds such as astaxanthin, curcumin, diallyl trisulfide, epigallocatechin gallate, ferulsinaic acid, fisetin, myricetin, rosmarinic acid, tannic acid, tyrosol, lipoic acid, α -lipoic acid (LA) and α -linolenic acid (ALA), and other essential fatty acids that can delay the natural ageing. This has been proved by *in-vivo* antiageing studies of them on model organisms (Argyropoulou et al., 2013). Among these compounds, LA and ALA based antiageing formulations are in high demand (Magalhães et al., 2017). The present study investigates an interesting method of liposomal encapsulation for the combined delivery of LA and ALA through daily consumption using a beverage model.

LA or 1, 2-dithiolane-3-pentanoic acid is generally found in meat muscle, fruits and vegetables. It has nowadays been recognized as an important bioactive compound in dietary supplements. LA is well known for its therapeutic benefits such as antioxidant activity, antidiabetic potency, remedial action in peripheral neuropathy, use in dermal care, and as an important geriatric supplement (by restoring depleting glutathione levels) (Salehi et al., 2019). Being a medically and nutritionally valued biomolecule, its pre-delivery sustenance and site-specific delivery in the body are important aspects.

ALA is an essential ω -3 polyunsaturated fatty acid that can be supplemented in the human body only through diet. *In vitro*, *in-vivo* and clinical trials suggest beneficial effects of ω -3 fatty acids including prevention and sometimes in the treatment of cardiac and circulatory disorders, cognitive disorders, inflammatory disorders, and immune dysfunction (Lavanya et al., 2019). Among all vegetable oil sources, chia seed oil (CO) contains around 68% of ALA (Elshafie et al., 2018). Therefore, in the current study chia oil has been chosen as the source of ALA.

Liposomes are being widely used in both research and industries of food sectors. Nowadays, liposomes are utilized for the delivery of bioactives such as nutraceuticals, antimicrobials, and flavors to food systems. Liposomal formulations have a number of advantages, e.g. entrapment and controlled release of hydrophilic, lipophilic, and amphiphilic materials, possibility of large-

scale production utilizing natural ingredients, as well as they render enhanced targetability (Dutta, Moses, & Anandharamakrishnan, 2019)

In our earlier research, the formulation of CO liposome and its detailed characterization including the sustained release of CO from its liposome has been published (Choudhary et al., 2021). In the present work, a combinatorial liposomal encapsulation of both CO and LA has been investigated to obtain a conjugate of ALA and LA for the secured delivery of both antioxidants. The aim was to encapsulate CO in the lipid bilayer of the liposome, and LA in the aqueous core. To achieve that an inclusion complex of LA in hydroxypropyl β -cyclodextrin (HP β CD) was formulated to solubilize LA in the buffer; whereas, CO was directly added in the lipid phase of the liposome. The liposome containing both CO and LA was characterized and incorporated into milk for fortification with ALA and LA. Since milk is an ideal carrier of food bioactive ingredients (Sharma, 2005), and cow milk is the most common source of milk globally, it has been chosen in our study for the delivery of nanoliposome. The shelf-life study of the liposome incorporated milk was also conducted to ensure its storability. The objective was thus to achieve a salutary dairy product rich in LA and ALA.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Cold-pressed chia oil and standardized milk (4.5 % fat, 8.5% solids-not-fat) were procured from the local market at Thanjavur, India. Soya phosphatidylcholine (30%), LA, HP β CD, dialysis membrane (cellulose, 12 kDa) and Tween 80 were purchased from Himedia, India. All chemicals used in the current work were of AR grade.

2.2. Formulation of LA-HP β CD inclusion complex

HP β CD is a well-known wall material to encapsulate various food bioactives for enhancing the functional properties in pharmaceutical sciences (Malanga et al., 2016). Lavanya et al. have used HP β CD for the formulation of β -carotene inhalable powders (Lavanya et al., 2019) and this wall material has also been used for enhancing the water solubility of permethrin by Yang et al. (2006). LA-HP β CD inclusion complex was prepared in the present study using the method reported by Racz et al. (2013) for preparation of LA- β CD, with few modifications.

Briefly, 300 mg LA was first dissolved in 5 mL of ethanol and then slowly added in 40 mL of HP β CD aqueous solution with continuous stirring. The ratio of LA and HP β CD was varied in the range of 1:1 - 1:5 to obtain maximum encapsulation of LA in HP β CD. The LA-HP β CD solution was stirred at 23 \pm 2 °C for 24 h. Ethanol was then evaporated from the mixture by drying in a water bath at 38 °C. The inclusion complex thus obtained was stored at 4 \pm 2 °C for further analyses.

2.3. Characterization of LA-HP β CD inclusion complex

2.3.1. Encapsulation efficiency

The encapsulation efficiency (EE) of LA-HP β CD inclusion complex was evaluated by dissolving a fixed amount of inclusion complex in a mixture of ethanol and 2% acetic acid solution (ethanol: acetic acid=1:2) in accordance with the literature (Vidović et al., 2015). The encapsulated LA was quantified in this mixture by UV-Vis spectrophotometer (multimode microplate reader, SpectraMax iD3, Molecular Devices, US) at 330 nm, using the standard curve of LA. The %EE was calculated by the following equation:

$$\% \text{ Encapsulation efficiency of LA} = \frac{\text{Total LA in encapsulate}}{\text{Theoretical LA}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

2.3.2. Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy

To detect any chemical reaction between the compounds during the preparation of the inclusion complex, FT-IR profiles of HP β CD, LA and inclusion complex were recorded using FT-IR spectrophotometer (Spectrum 100, Perkin Elmer, US), at a scanning range of 500-4000/cm (scan speed 0.2 cm/s; resolution 4.0; number of scans 10).

2.3.3. X-ray powder diffraction (XRD)

To examine the crystallinity of HP β CD, LA and LA-HP β CD inclusion complex, XRD diffraction patterns were obtained using X-ray diffractometer (XPert3, Malvern Panalytical Ltd., UK) at an angular range of $2\theta = 2\text{-}40^\circ$. The samples were analyzed using CuK α radiation with a wavelength of 1.544 Å.

2.3.4. Proton (^1H) NMR spectroscopy

To examine the dynamics and structural changes during inclusion, NMR spectra of HP β CD, LA and inclusion complex were recorded using Bruker Advance 500 spectrometer. For NMR

analysis, the inclusion complex of HP β CD along with the active substance LA was dissolved in D₂O. The samples were kept at 25°C for 15 min to achieve a thermal equilibrium before analysis. The operating conditions for NMR spectroscopy were as follows: 32 K data points, 10.1 μ s pulse of 90°, 2 s for each scan (16 scans) with a resolution of 0.588 Hz per point. The chemical shifts obtained in the spectrum were expressed in parts per million (ppm).

2.3.5. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis

To understand the thermal properties of the LA-HP β CD inclusion complex, DSC analysis was conducted using DSC 3 STAR^e System (Mettler Toledo, Hong Kong). For that, 4-8 mg sample was taken in a DSC pan (empty pan as the reference). The sample was heated from 25 °C to 350 °C @ 10 °C/min (Racz et al., 2013). The experiment was performed under nitrogen with a constant flow rate of 40 mL/min.

2.4. Loading of inclusion complex in CO nanoliposome

To load the LA-HP β CD inclusion complex in the CO liposome, HP β CD was dissolved in 40 mL of PBS buffer, and the inclusion complex was prepared in the optimized ratio of ALA and HP β CD (1:5) at room temperature. The free LA was separated from the inclusion complex by centrifugation at 5000 rpm. This inclusion complex in PBS buffer was used as the aqueous phase during liposome preparation.

The nanoliposome was prepared by thin film hydration method at the optimized conditions published (Choudhary et al., 2021). The thin film of lipid obtained from soya phosphatidylcholine and Tween 80 (1:1) (containing 1 g CO) was hydrated using inclusion complex (in PBS) and nanoliposomes were formulated using a probe sonicator (PRO 650, Labman Scientific Instruments Private Limited, Chennai, India). The nanoliposome thus obtained (LA-HP β CD-in CO) was dialyzed against PBS buffer (pH 7.0, 50 mM) for 24 h to separate the encapsulated CO and inclusion complex from the unencapsulated one (Choudhary et al., 2021).

2.5. Characterization of LA-HP β CD-in CO nanoliposome

2.5.1. Estimation of CO and LA content in nanoliposomes

In order to evaluate the bioactive content of nanoliposome, the CO and LA were extracted from dialyzed liposomes using the method followed by Viriyaraj et al. (2009). Briefly,

1 mL dialyzed liposome was added with 5 mL of chloroform and extracted for 5 min. This solution was then filtered using a 0.45 μm membrane (Millipore) and kept for 24 h for complete extraction of entrapped active compounds. After that, the amount of encapsulated CO was estimated at 300 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. LA was estimated by the method previously mentioned in section 2.3.1.

2.5.2. Morphology

The morphology of the LA-HP β CD-in-CO nanoliposome was scanned by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM). A thin layer of nanoliposome was casted on a glass coverslip and kept for overnight drying in a desiccator. Subsequently, the sample was gold-coated using an auto fine coater (SC7620- Mini Sputter Coater, Quorum, UK), then examined for its morphology with SUPRA 55VP, Gemini Column at 5 kV (Carl Zeiss Germany).

2.5.3. Size distribution and zeta potential of nanoliposomes

The size distribution and zeta potential of LA-HP β CD-in-CO nanoliposome were investigated using Zetasizer (Nano ZS90, Malvern Instruments Pvt. Ltd., UK) at 23 ± 2 °C.

2.5.4. FT-IR spectroscopy

The FT-IR spectrum of nanoliposome was recorded according to the method discussed in section 2.3.2.

2.5.5. Estimation of ALA content in nanoliposome

The ALA content of nanoliposome was estimated following the method detailed by Choudhary et al. (2021). Briefly, the fat from the nanoliposome was extracted and converted into fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) (ISO 5509:2000). This FAME was analyzed for ALA content by gas chromatography flame ionization detector (GC-FID) (GC-2010 Plus, Shimadzu, Japan) using capillary column (Rt-2560 column biscyanopropyl polysiloxane) following the method ISO 12966-2 (2011) (Dong, Hu, Chu, Zhao, & Tan, 2017).

2.6. Incorporation of LA-HP β CD-in-CO nanoliposomes in milk

The cow milk was fortified using LA-HP β CD-in-CO nanoliposomes (liposome: milk= 1:4) to meet the RDA of LA (300 mg) and ALA (1.6 g) in one serving of milk (240 mL). The

fortified milk sample was homogenized with high speed homogenizer (IKA T25) at 5000 rpm. Then the milk was pasteurized at 72 °C for 15 s, cooled, aseptically bottled, and stored in glass bottles at 4±1 °C for 7 days for shelf life study. The physicochemical analyses of milk samples were conducted on 0, 2, 4, and 7th days of the storage. To circumvent the hydrolytic degradation of milk during sampling, 4 sets of milk samples were stored separately for each sampling point. The control sample, i.e., milk without nanoliposome was also stored under the same conditions.

2.7. Estimation of physicochemical properties of stored milk samples

2.7.1. Titratable acidity and pH

The AOAC official method 942.15 (AOAC, 2000) was used for determining the acidity. For analysis of titratable acidity, 10 mL of milk sample was taken and titrated with 0.1 N NaOH using 0.5% phenolphthalein as an indicator. The titratable acidity was expressed in terms of ‘g of lactic acid/100 g product’. The pH of the milk sample was measured using a digital pH meter (PC 700, Eutech Instrument, Singapore) at 23±2 °C.

2.7.2. Colour value

The color of milk samples was estimated by Hunter color lab (D25 Optical sensor, Hunter Associate Laboratory, Reston, VA) and results were presented in L* (lightness) ranges from 0 (black) to 100 (white), a* (redness) ranges from -60 (red) to +60 (green) and b* (yellowness) ranges from -60 (yellow) to +60 (blue).

2.7.3. Viscosity measurement

The viscosity of liposome enriched milk along with control was evaluated using an automatic digital rotational viscometer with RE-77107 spindle at 23±2 °C (Visco Pack B, ATAGO, India).

2.7.4. Peroxide value

The peroxide value (PV) of milk samples was examined to evaluate the level of primary metabolites during storage. PV of milk samples was estimated according to the procedure reported by Shantha and Decker (1994). Before estimation of PV, total fat was extracted from milk samples according to the method used by Bligh and Dyer (1959) for extraction of fat from biological materials.

Briefly, 30-40 mg extracted fat was added in 9.8 mL chloroform/methanol mixture (7:3, v/v), then ammonium thiocyanate (50 μ L) and ferrous chloride (50 μ L) were added to the mixture. The solution was mixed in a vortex for 5 min at 23 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C and kept in dark for 5 min. After that, the absorbance was recorded using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer at 500 nm. The PV was calculated using the standard curve of Fe (III).

$$PV(\text{mEq O}_2 / \text{kg fat}) = \frac{\text{Abs}}{55.84 \times w} \times \frac{1}{b} \quad (2)$$

Where, w is the weight of the oil, Abs is the absorbance, b is the slope of the Fe (III) standard curve, and 55.84 is the atomic weight of Fe (III).

2.7.5. *p*-anisidine and TOTOX value

The *p*-anisidine value (AV) of milk samples represents the generation of secondary oxidation products during the storage. To estimate AV, lipid from milk was extracted by the method mentioned in the previous section (section 2.7.4). Subsequently, the AV values of the milk samples were estimated by AOAC official method (Cd 18-19) (AOAC, 2004). The supernatants of the lipid extracts were collected and their absorbance values (E_a) were recorded at 350 nm by spectrophotometer using isooctane as blank. Then, 5 mL of supernatants were mixed with the same volume of isooctane in Pyrex test tubes. This mix was treated with 1 mL of *p*-anisidine solution (0.25% in glacial acetic acid). The test tubes were capped properly and vigorously shaken and incubated in dark for 10 min. The absorbance (E_b) of supernatant with anisidine against isooctane (mixed with *p*-anisidine) was recorded at 350 nm. The AV was calculated as the equation (Eq. 3) given below. Total oxidation (primary and secondary) of the milk samples were also studied by estimation of TOTOX value using Eq. 4 (Maduko et al., 2008).

$$AV = \frac{25 \times (12E_b - E_a)}{\text{Sample weight}} \quad (3)$$

$$TOTOX \text{ value} = 2 PV + AV \quad (4)$$

2.7.6. Fatty acid profile

The fat from all the milk samples was extracted using chloroform-methanol (2:1, v/v) and the extracted sample was converted to fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) as per the method mentioned in section 2.5.6. Fatty acid profile was analyzed using the FAME by gas

chromatography-mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) (436-GC Bruker, Livingston, UK). GC-MS analysis was conducted with a 2 μ L (split mode 10:1) sample volume using capillary column (5% diphenyl /95% dimethyl polysiloxane, 30 m x 0.25mm ID x 0.25 μ m). The inlet temperature was at 280 $^{\circ}$ C. The program for oven temperature was: 50 $^{\circ}$ C for 1 min, 50 to 175 $^{\circ}$ C @25 $^{\circ}$ C/min, then increased to 230 $^{\circ}$ C @ 4 $^{\circ}$ C/min; and isothermal hold at 230 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 min (Rasti, Erfanian, & Selamat, 2017). The total run time was 26 min for each analysis.

2.8. Statistical Analysis

All experiments were conducted in triplicate, and the data are expressed as means \pm standard deviation (SD) of three independent experimental runs. Duncan's multiple range tests with $p < 0.05$ were performed with SPSS statistics software (IBM, USA; version 20) to verify the significance of all tests.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Encapsulation efficiency of LA-HP β CD inclusion complex

The EE of inclusion complexes revealed enhanced encapsulation of LA with an increasing amount of HP β CD (Table 1). Notably, below 1:4.5 (LA: HP β CD), the formation of inclusion complex was not observed, as confirmed by the precipitation of LA; probably due to insufficient HP β CD for accommodating LA. Since the driving forces responsible for the complex formation are hydrogen bonds, Van der Waal forces, and hydrophobic forces between drug and HP β CD, an appropriate amount of HP β CD is necessary for complex formation. Maximum EE of 86.09% was recorded when the ratio of LA: HP β CD was 1:4.70. Any further increase of HP β CD decreased EE and caused precipitation of surplus HP β CD. Also, an increase in LA to 400 mg in the ratio of 1:4.7 did not increase the EE. Similar to the current finding, Kim et al. (2020) also reported 83.37% EE for flavonoid-HP β CD inclusion complex. In another study, the inclusion complex prepared with curcumin: β -CD (2:1) resulted in 97.28% recovery of curcumin (Tang et al., 2002). These findings reveal that the amount of drug encapsulated in the inclusion complex depends on the type of drug and the form of β CD.

3.2. Characterization of inclusion complex

3.2.1. FTIR analysis

The FTIR spectra of LA, HP β CD and the inclusion complex have been presented in Figure 1. The wide band between 4,000 and 3,000 cm^{-1} in all the samples, except LA and CO, represents O-H stretching vibrations. Owing to the complex formation between LA and HP β CD, several shifting in bands were observed. The broad and strong absorption band at 3391.55 cm^{-1} in HP β CD was shifted to 3411.72 cm^{-1} in inclusion complex due to the formation of additional hydrogen bonds (Racz et al., 2013). The absorption at 2925.88 cm^{-1} represents CH_3 groups in spectra of inclusion complex which was observed at 2927.93 cm^{-1} in pure HP β CD. The peak at 1634.11 cm^{-1} (O-H bending) in HP β CD shifted to 1632.47 cm^{-1} in inclusion complex (Wei et al., 2017).

The strong band at 1692.99 cm^{-1} that stands for C=O vibration in LA was shifted to 1632.47 cm^{-1} in the inclusion complex. The absorption peaks at 945.28 and 1240.82 cm^{-1} represent O-H groups in LA, shifted to 949.24 and 1448.53 cm^{-1} , respectively, in inclusion complex. Further, the absorption peaks at 3027.23 and 520.53 cm^{-1} that denote O-H group and S-S group respectively in LA (Bai & Hu, 2014; Ikuta et al., 2013; Jullian, Moyano, Yañez, & Oleazar, 2007) are absent in the inclusion complex due to the encapsulation of LA in HP β CD. The major reason for the shifting of bands was the formation of hydrogen bonds between HP β CD and LA in the inclusion complex (Liu & Guo, 2002).

3.2.2. XRD profile

The XRD profile of inclusion complex showed the presence of both crystalline and amorphous phases (Fig. 2). The diffraction pattern of LA showed sharp peaks at diffraction angles (2θ) of 15.04°, 20.80°, 23.92°, 25.50° and 44.40°, establishing the crystalline nature of LA. Few of these peaks (23.92° & 25.50°) were also observed in the inclusion complex with shift showing retention of the crystalline form of LA. However, some of the peaks (15.04° and 44.40°) present in LA were masked by HP β CD in the complex that indicates inclusion of LA in the cavity of HP β CD. The presence of a broad peak between 15 to 25° in HP β CD and inclusion complex indicates the amorphous nature. This amorphous peak of HP β CD was also reported by Kim (2020). The presence of crystalline and amorphous phases in powder diffraction patterns was earlier reported by Ikuta et al. (2013) for LA- α CD complex and Racz et al. (2012) for LA-

β CD. The change in crystallinity of LA in inclusion complex is an important indication of the inclusion of LA in HP β CD.

3.2.3. NMR spectroscopy

In the NMR spectrum of LA, major peaks were observed at 3.48, 2.25, 2.08, 1.03, 1.10, and 0.99 ppm; whereas for HP β CD, major peaks were visible at 3.50, 2.50, 2.95, 1.53, and 1.00 ppm. Similar to FT-IR and XRD data, shifting of peaks was also observed in NMR spectrum indicating the formation of a strong inclusion complex between LA and HP β CD. In the inclusion complex, major peaks were found at 3.60, 3.30, 2.89, 2.50, 2.20 and 1.00 ppm. The shifting of peaks in HP β CD may be owing to the presence of a 5member ring in the cavity of dextrin (Gannimani et al., 2015; Yuan & Xu, 2012). Racz et al. (2013) also reported the shifting of peaks of LA in its inclusion complex.

3.2.4. DSC analysis

In the DSC thermogram of LA, a sharp endothermic peak was observed at 62.48 °C which represents its degradation temperature (Fig. 4). This melting peak is the characteristic peak of LA and the finding is in accordance with Li, Kim, Reddy, Lee, & Lim (2019). The absence of this melting peak in the thermogram of inclusion complex indicates the inclusion of LA in the bucket-like structure of HP β CD that protected LA from degradation. The same finding was observed by Racz et al. (2013) for LA inclusion complex with β CD, and Takahashi, Bungo, & Mikuni, (2011) for LA complex with G2- β CD. The sharp melting of HP β CD at 192.13 °C shifted to 186.5 °C in inclusion complex owing to the embedment of LA in HP β CD cavity (Fig. 4). This shifting of degradation peak of HP β CD was also reported by Kim et al. (2020) for flavonoid-HP β CD inclusion complex.

3.3. Characterization of LA-HP β CD-in-CO nanoliposome

3.3.1. CO and LA content

The contents of CO and LA in the nanoliposome were estimated to be 20.06 \pm 0.11 mg/mL and 4.92 \pm 0.03 mg/mL, respectively, indicating EE of 80.24 \pm 0.49% and 76.38 \pm 0.58% for CO and LA liposome, respectively. The EE of CO nanoliposome earlier was found to be 88.31 \pm 0.64% (Choudhary et al., 2021), which decreased in the current study, possibly owing to

the competitive encapsulation of LA and CO in the lipid bilayer. The obtained data correlates with that of Shchelkonogov et al., (2016) who reported 85% inclusion of LA when liposome was prepared using soy phosphatidylholine. In a different study, Maiti et al. (2007) reported 60% and 55% EE for α -tocopheryl-lipoic acid conjugates (TL1 and TL2) when nanovesicles were prepared for doxorubicin delivery. Furthermore, LA liposome prepared with soy phosphatidylholine and cholesterol showed 70% EE (Maiti et al., 2007).

3.3.2. Morphology

The FESEM image exhibited the spherical shape of LA-HP β CD-in-CO nanoliposome with an average particle size ≤ 200 nm (Fig. 5). The morphology showed few elongated particles with distortion from spherical shape owing to the formation of the rigid structure of LA in lipid bilayer. Spherical shape of liposome was also reported for LA and coenzyme Q10 nanoliposome prepared with soy phosphatidylcholine, cholesterol and Tween 80 in the study conducted by Zhao et al. (2015). Aadinath, Bhushani, & Anandharamakrishnan, (2016) reported similar morphology and particle size for curcumin-in- β -cyclodextrin-in-nanomagnetoliposomes.

3.3.3. Size distribution and zeta potential

The zetasizer results revealed that LA-HP β CD-in-CO nanoliposome possessed a narrow range of particle size (10 to 200 nm) with uniform distribution and an average diameter of 52.1 ± 7.0 nm. The polydispersity index (PDI) of 0.175 proved a good monodispersity of nanoliposomes. The zeta potential of nanoliposomes was found to be -15.8 mV (i.e. >15 mV) indicating strong electrostatic repulsion between particles of nanoliposomes which is required for stability of nanoliposomes (Goh & Giap, 2010).

3.3.4. ALA content of nanoliposome

The ALA content of LA-HP β CD-in-CO nanoliposome was 1.48%, i.e. 14.99 mg/mL ALA is present in nanoliposome. A similar result (16.5 mg/mL) has also been obtained by Choudhary et al. (2021) for CO nanoliposome. It is indicating a liposomal formulation with good content of ALA.

3.4. Physicochemical properties of nanoliposome enriched milk during storage

The physicochemical properties of stored milk samples (control and liposome-enriched test sample) are presented in Table 2. A significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed in the pH

of the control and nanoliposome-enriched (test) sample. The initial pH of control and test samples was 6.61 ± 0.01 and 6.90 ± 0.01 , respectively. The initial acidity of control and test samples was 0.15 ± 0.01 and $0.13 \pm 0.01\%$, respectively, in terms of lactic acid. The increased pH and decreased acidity of the test sample may be due to the pH of nanoliposome (7.20 ± 0.01) incorporated into the test sample. The pH of both the milk samples decreased with storage. The increased acidity could be due to the production of lactic acid in the milk. Such increase in acidity in the test sample was also been reported by Nagarajappa and Battula when milk sample was enriched with ω -3 fatty acid emulsion (Nagarajappa & Battula, 2017). During storage when the pH of milk attains a value in the range of 4-5, lactic acid bacteria in milk grow faster and produce lactic acid, which is the main reason for the deterioration of the milk quality. In the current study, the pH of both control and test samples was almost neutral indicating that both the milk samples were not spoiled during the storage period. Similar observations have been made by others as well for milk (Klaenhammer, 1988; Lu et al., 2013).

The viscosity of the test milk sample was slightly higher compared to control milk sample owing to the addition of nanoliposomes (Table 2). The significant increase ($p < 0.05$) during storage was due to the partial gelation of milk protein. A significant change ($p < 0.05$) was also observed in the color of both the milk samples. Similar to the acidity and viscosity, the PV and AV of test sample were also increased owing to the incorporation of nanoliposome due to the presence of unsaturated fatty acids in oil. Accordingly, the TOTOX values of test sample were also higher compared to control. The present results are in agreement with Chee et al., (2005) wherein yogurt supplemented with ω -3 fatty acid emulsion exhibited a higher level of oxidation during storage. Further, Rasti et al. (2017), Let et al. (2005) and Nagarajappa and Battula (2017) have also reported an increase in PV and AV of liposome-enriched milk.

Overall, the physiochemical properties of test sample were found to be significantly different from that of the control sample due to the addition of an adequate amount of nanoliposome to provide required amount of LA and ALA, i.e. 236.16 mg of LA and 719.52 mg of ALA in one serving of milk (240 mL).

3.5. Fatty acid profile of test sample during storage

From the fatty acid profiles of control and test milk samples, it was observed that the contents of linolenic acid and linoleic acid were increased in the nanoliposome enriched test sample; whereas, certain fatty acids such as decanoic acid, lauric acid, palmitoleic acid, and oleic acid were decreased significantly in comparison with control sample (Table 3). This variation in fatty acids' content in test milk samples is clearly due to the addition of nanoliposome in milk.

Interestingly, no significant ($p > 0.05$) change was observed in the content of decanoic acid, lauric acid, and palmitoleic acid during the 7 days of storage of test sample (Table 3). Among saturated fatty acids, myristic acid content increased slightly. Serafeimidou, Zlatanov, Kritikos, & Tourianis, (2013) has also observed an increase in saturated fatty acid content during storage of cow milk yogurt. The study conducted by Nagarajappa and Battula (2017) on fortification of milk with flaxseed oil liposome reported an increase in linolenic acid after fortification, and no significant change was found during 7 days' storage period. Further, a study conducted by Lim, Norziah, and Lu (2010) on fortification of ice cream by flaxseed oil reported a slight decrease in linolenic acid content during 21 days of storage. The decrease in unsaturated fatty acids in this study may be due to the oxidative breakdown of fatty acids during storage as suggested by other researchers (Gulla & Waghray, 2011). The decrease and increase in fatty acid content may depend on the type of food system as well as the type of fortificant selected for the study.

4. Conclusion

The incorporation of chia oil based lipoic acid nanoliposomal formulation into milk did have a positive effect in terms of adding value to the cow milk, and in rendering greater sustenance of the functionality over 7 days. The find highlighted the key attributes of encapsulation that include $86.09 \pm 2.17\%$ efficiency (for lipoic acid inclusion complex with HP β CD), $80.24 \pm 0.49\%$ for α -lipoic acid, and $76.38 \pm 0.58\%$ for chia oil. The nanoliposomal particle size was 52.19 ± 7.0 nm, and particles showed good monodispersity. Value addition of milk through fortification with the liposomal complex revealed 236.16 mg lipoic acid and 719.52 mg α -linolenic acid in one serving (240 mL) of milk, and shelf stability for at least a week (at 4 ± 1 °C). Thus, this formulation can be used for the supplementation of both of these bioactives as a means of new and alternate techniques for cow milk fortification.

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Figure

Fig. 1. FT-IR profiles of different components of LA-HPβCD-in-CO nanoliposome (CO: chia oil, LA: lipoic acid, IC: inclusion complex)

Fig. 2. XRD graph for lipoic acid (LA), hydroxypropyl β -cyclodextrin (HP β CD) and inclusion complex (IC)

Fig. 4. DSC thermograms of lipoic acid, HPβCD and inclusion complex

200 nm EHT = 5.00 kV Signal A = SE2 Date :22 Dec 2020
WD = 7.2 mm Mag = 200.00 K X Time :15:55:54

Fig. 5. FE-SEM image of LA-HP β CD-in-CO nanoliposome

Table 1. Encapsulation efficiency of lipoic acid (LA) in inclusion complex

Components of inclusion complex			Encapsulation efficiency*
LA (mg)	HP β CD (mg)	LA: HP β CD	(%)
300	1290	1:4.5	58.70 \pm 0.40 ^d
	1410	1:4.7	86.09 \pm 2.17 ^a
	1500	1:5.0	72.95 \pm 0.79 ^c
	2250	1:7.5	77.78 \pm 0.11 ^b
400	1880	1:4.7	60.01 \pm 0.37 ^d

*Different letters in a column indicate significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 2. Physiochemical properties of milk samples during storage

Days	Sample name	Acidity (%LA)	pH	Viscosity (cP)	PV [#]	AV ^{##}	TOTOX value ^{###}	L*	a*	b*
0	Control	0.15±0.01 ^b	6.61±0.01 ^a	1.95±0.005 ^b	0.279±0.060 ^b	0.233±0.018 ^a	0.79 ^c	92.236±0.005 ^c	-1.163±0.005 ^c	10.110±0.005 ^d
	Test sample	0.13±0.01 ²	6.90±0.01 ¹	2.03±0.005 ⁴	0.512±0.080 ³	0.405±0.032 ²	1.43 ⁴	89.523±0.005 ³	-1.473±0.005 ⁴	11.320±0.005 ⁴
2	Control	0.17±0.01 ^{ab}	6.60±0.01 ^b	1.98±0.01 ^{ab}	0.313±0.040 ^a	0.227±0.006 ^a	0.85 ^b	92.500±0.005 ^b	-0.806±0.020 ^a	11.050±0.010 ^c
	Test sample	0.15±0.02 ^{1,2}	6.87±0.01 ²	2.09±0.005 ³	0.539±0.06 ²	0.413±0.010 ²	1.49 ³	90.530±0.043 ²	-1.100±0.010 ²	11.740±0.028 ³
4	Control	0.19±0.01 ^{ab}	6.56±0.01 ^c	1.99±0.005 ^{ab}	0.324±0.05 ^a	0.229±0.010 ^a	0.88 ^{ab}	93.916±0.005 ^a	-0.776±0.005 ^a	13.016±0.011 ^a
	Test sample	0.18±0.01 ^{1,2}	6.66±0.01 ³	2.12±0.01 ²	0.551±0.061 ^{1,2}	0.452±0.020 ^{1,2}	1.55 ²	92.676±0.005 ¹	-0.973±0.005 ¹	11.926±0.005 ¹
7	Control	0.22±0.01 ^a	6.49±0.04 ^d	2.10±0.10 ^a	0.337±0.016 ^a	0.245±0.014 ^a	0.92 ^a	92.223±0.007 ^c	-0.973±0.005 ^b	11.296±0.005 ^b
	Test sample	0.19±0.01 ²	6.61±0.03 ⁴	2.26±0.01 ¹	0.560±0.040 ¹	0.473±0.017 ¹	1.59 ¹	90.533±0.043 ²	-1.213±0.005 ³	12.243±0.005 ²

[#]PV: Peroxide value in meq of O₂/kg fat

^{##}AV: *p*-Anisidine value

^{###}Calculated from the average values of PV and AV

Different letters and numbers in a column indicate significant difference at p≤0.05

Table 3. Fatty acid profile (% peak area) of nanoliposome enriched milk during storage

Fatty acids	Control sample	Nanoliposome	Test sample*			
			0 th day	2 nd day	4 th day	7 th day
Decanoic acid	2.04	-	1.17 ^a	1.17 ^a	1.16 ^a	1.16 ^a
Lauric acid	3.00	4.61	1.89 ^a	1.90 ^a	1.88 ^a	1.86 ^a

Myristic acid	12.29	4.33	12.14 ^a	12.45 ^b	12.45 ^b	12.47 ^b
Palmitic acid	46.49	11.10	46.39 ^a	46.25 ^b	46.18 ^c	46.16 ^c
Palmitoleic acid	1.36	-	0.79 ^a	0.77 ^a	0.77 ^a	0.75 ^a
Stearic acid	10.08	3.48	10.09 ^a	10.02 ^b	9.96 ^c	9.91 ^c
Oleic acid	23.28	16.22	22.61 ^a	22.31 ^b	21.95 ^c	21.98 ^c
Linoleic acid	0.93	26.90	1.48 ^a	1.45 ^b	1.42 ^c	1.40 ^c
Linolenic acid	0.10	33.20	3.66 ^a	3.64 ^{ab}	3.63 ^{ab}	3.61 ^b

*Different letters in a row indicate significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$